

chamber at 20-25 °C and a 12-h day/night NUV light cycle. Pathogenicity tests were carried out.

Twenty fungi genera were identified (see table). *H. oryzae* was the most common fungus isolated. Pathogenicity tests reproduced typical grain discoloration symptoms. ■

Integrated pest management — insects

Leaffolder (LF) outbreak in Punjab, Pakistan

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The rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Gn), long considered a minor pest of rice in Pakistan, has attained the status of a major pest in the last few years, and has caused considerable losses to the rice crop. During the 1989-90 crop season, the pest multiplied enormously, with severe incidence observed during Aug-Sep.

We conducted a survey of LF incidence on 2,941 ricefields at 73 locations in eight rice-producing districts of the Punjab.

The crop was severely damaged in Sheikhupura, Sialkot, and Gujranwala Districts (see figure). Infestation was 51% at Dirdhe Dogran in Sheikhupura. In Sialkot, Jassarwala showed 25% infestation. In Faisalabad, Okara, Kasur, Lahore, and Gujrat Districts, infestations were less than 10%.

About 80% of the rice area was planted to Basmati 385, a fine, aromatic,

Leaffolder incidence in the Punjab, 1989.

Leaffolder infestation as affected by different factors in ricefields. Punjab, Pakistan, 1989-90.

	Infestation (%)							
	Variety				Cultural		Environmental	
	Basmati 370	Basmati 385	Kashmira	Palman	Early crop	Late crop	Shady areas	Nonshaded areas
	13.7	15.6	5.3	70.3	10.3	35.0	40.7	13.7
	10.9	15.5	4.7	45.9	7.5	23.5	55.9	13.9
	15.1	16.2	8.5	85.0	7.2	27.2	72.3	15.3
	15.7	20.5	7.2	40.5	6.3	39.1	42.0	17.2
	8.5	13.4	6.3	57.9	13.8	40.2	45.9	10.3
	10.7	10.6	3.4	55.9	10.9	24.3	65.1	20.5
	17.2	19.7	6.3	55.0	12.1	20.5	70.5	17.2
	8.7	20.3	3.7	47.5	9.0	29.5	69.2	21.0
	11.5	17.5	5.6	69.7	13.4	40.0	50.1	15.3
	14.5	16.7	5.8	45.2	8.5	22.2	49.5	10.2
Mean	12.7	16.6	5.7	57.3	9.9	30.2	56.1	15.5

and high-yielding variety. Average damage to this crop was 16.6%; damage on Basmati 370, Kashmira, and Palman was 12.7, 5.7, and 57.3%, respectively

(see table). Infestation in the late crop was higher than in the early crop. Infestation in shady areas was much higher than in nonshaded areas. ■

Sugarcane pest found in Sulawesi ricefields

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The sugarcane mite *Aceria* (= *Eriophyes*) *saccharini* (Wang) was

first reported in Java by van Hall in 1923. It was discovered on rice at Maros Experimental Farm in 1988. Damage symptoms had been noticed for several years before identification.

In 1989, the mite damaged more than 775 ha of rice in South and Central Sulawesi. Rice plants show brownish yellowing leaves about 3-4 wk after

transplanting. In heavier infestations, plants exhibit stunting. Up to 1,000 mites/leaf can occur. Infestations are heavier in the dry season.

Indonesian rice varieties Cisadane, Pelita I-1, and Cisanggurang are more resistant to the mite than are IR26, IR42, IR48, and IR64. ■